

Geometry Adaptive 3D Semantic Segmentation for Autonomous Driving with Continual Learning

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I. ABSTRACT

Autonomous driving vehicles rely heavily on accurate scene understanding, including semantic segmentation of 3D point clouds. With this short paper we want to address the need for robust and adaptive algorithms in autonomous driving. We present a novel approach to semantic segmentation that has been developed through our ongoing research. Our method leverages 3D sparse convolutions based on MinkowskiEngine and a continual learning framework. The core concept involves granting the vehicle the capacity to dynamically adjust to varying spatial environments. This idea is realized by breaking down the primary task into 3D reconstruction *and* semantic segmentation. We utilize the vehicle’s ego-motion estimation to accumulate multiple point clouds, enabling a deeper understanding of the scene’s geometry.

Index Terms—Semantic segmentation, 3D point clouds, Sparse convolutions, Continual learning, 3D reconstruction.

II. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of autonomous driving vehicles, one of the critical challenges is enabling these vehicles to perceive and understand their surrounding environment accurately. This comprehension is essential for making real-time decisions, ensuring safety, and optimizing navigation. A fundamental task in this context is semantic segmentation, which involves categorizing the various elements in the vehicle’s field of view, such as roads, pedestrians, vehicles, and so on.

While the importance of semantic segmentation for autonomous vehicles is clear, achieving precise and real-time segmentation in complex 3D environments poses significant challenges. Traditional approaches may struggle with the dynamic and diverse nature of real-world driving scenarios, which can include varying weather conditions, lighting, and unpredictable road layouts. State-Of-The-Art (SOTA) semantic segmentation methods, like Cylinder3D [2], (AF)2-S3Net [3], RPNNet [4], Point-Voxel-KD [5], 2DPass [6], are prone to bad performance when trained on specific dataset and sensor and tested on a different dataset, with a data distribution that does not match the training set or acquired with a similar but slightly different sensor. It is the case of SOTA methods trained on SemanticKITTI dataset [1], which is acquired

Fig. 1. An illustrative example of the output of our system using as input a query scene from the test set (sequence 08) of SemanticKITTI dataset [1]. This point cloud is much more dense with respect to the original cloud. This density increase is due to our methodology, which involves reconstructing the accumulation of past and current point clouds by leveraging the ego-motion of the vehicle. We employ a Nearest Neighbor search to label the input point cloud from the dense labeled cloud.

with a Velodyne HDL-64E LiDAR. This sensor is a 360-degree rotating LiDAR with 64 channels, with a $26,8^\circ$ uniform Vertical Field of View (VFOV). Uniform means that the 64 fibers of the sensor are equally spaced. A different test dataset can be, for example, PandaSet [7]. This dataset is acquired with a Panda64 LiDAR, which is very similar to the HDL-64E but has a gradient VFOV of 40° . Gradient means that the fibers are not equally spaced. Even though the two sensors exhibits a minimal discrepancy, this is not negligible and very often this, in conjunction with the different framed environment, causes the model to degrade the performance. Therefore, there is a pressing need for advanced methods that can adapt to these dynamic environments and consistently provide accurate semantic segmentation.

We directly tackle this problem and propose a new neural network architecture for semantic segmentation based on 3D sparse convolutions and a new domain adaptation strategy that allows to dynamically adapt the weights of the learned model to the new distribution of the spatial environment in which the autonomous vehicle is operating. Our architecture relies on PU-Dense [8], a novel geometry upsampling technique that

hierarchically reconstructs an upsampled point cloud geometry via progressive rescaling and multiscale feature extraction. The framework employs a U-Net type architecture that downscales the point cloud to a bottleneck and then upscales it to a higher level-of-detail point cloud.

In this short paper, we first formally describe the semantic segmentation problem, then we will briefly introduce our proposed new architecture and domain adaptation strategy.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Problem Formulation

Let $(P, L) = \{\{p_i, r_i\}, c_i\}$ be N unordered points of a point cloud where $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the i -th input point coordinates (x , y and z), r_i is the remission value of point i , $c_i \in \mathbb{N}^m$ is the semantic class label, where m is the number of all possible semantic class labels. With this notation, P represents the set of the 3D coordinates and L the semantic class label set of each point p in the point cloud P . The goal is to learn a function $F(\cdot, \theta)$, parameterized by θ , that takes input feature (p_i, r_i) and assigns a semantic label for each point. Let θ be the weights and parameters of our learning neural model learned during the training process. Moreover, the function F is required to be as general as possible: across multiple datasets acquired with different sensors, we want F to be consistent with the ground truth semantic labelling of the point clouds.

In our work, we de-couple the learning of F into two different learning domains: geometry understanding and labeling. We make the following assumption: a model that is able to understand the geometry of the scene will also be able to label the point cloud of the surrounding environment.

Let P_t represent the current point cloud, which is essentially the most recent LiDAR sensor reading. Let P_{t-k} denote the point cloud acquired k point clouds back. Assuming we've accumulated a total of M point clouds, we can refer to this accumulation as the dense cloud, denoted as:

$$P_u = \bigcup_{k=0}^M P_{t-k} \quad (1)$$

Our new requirement for the function F is to enable the generation of the dense point cloud P_u using the current point cloud P_t as input (query).

In our work, we do not directly employ P_t and P_u for training F . Instead, we begin by downsampling them through voxelization and subsequently transfer the resulting labeling to the original P_t .

In Figure 1 we report a qualitative example of a segmented point cloud P_u .

B. Preprocessing

The preprocessing of the raw 3D point cloud data into a voxelized format P_v is cardinal in order to use 3D convolutions and learn 3D features. The first important difference introduced in our work is the input features f of each input point $p_i \in P_v$. Rather than feeding the network with the P_v only, we use the remission values as the initial feature value of

an occupied voxel, i.e. $f(x_i, y_i, z_i) = r_i$ (in the original work, the authors assigned each occupied voxel $f(x_i, y_i, z_i) = 1$). It is important to note that r_i is a real value such that $r_i \in [0, 1]$. As previously done, we assign $f(x_i, y_i, z_i) = 0$ if the voxel is not occupied.

We perform downsampling on both the query input point cloud P_t and the accumulated point cloud P_u using a voxel size of 5 cm. Additionally, prior to voxelization, we eliminate points from P_u that are distant from any point in P_t by more than 40 cm. This process is intended to generate a dense cloud P_u that contains points near to P_t , enabling our model to make predictions based on nearby points rather than distant ones that cannot be inferred from P_t .

C. System Description

The overview of our semantic segmentation framework is depicted in Figure 2. It is implemented using MinkowskiEngine [9] and it uses sparse convolution. The core part of the feature extraction module is based on a multiscale U-Net [10] encoder-decoder architecture.

The first layer is convolution with kernel-size 5 (for a great receptive field) and a Feature Extraction (FE) Unit. Details of the latter layer are explained in [8]. An FE Unit is a sequence of: Inception Residual Block (IRB), 3D Dilated Pyramid and again IRB. This layer does not modify the input/output number of channels, but instead focuses on extracting spatial features at multiple scales.

The encoder module comprises subsequent convolution layers with stride=2 (reducing the number of voxels in the input point cloud) and increasing number of channels, and FE Units to further process the information. The decoder part of the module is constituted of transposed convolution layers with stride=2 (increasing the number of voxels in the point cloud) and FE Units. As in the U-Net architecture, features from the encoder are aggregated (e.g., concatenated) to the features of the decoder in order to recover or integrate the fine-grained features lost during encoding and allowing skip-connection for the gradient computation. This enables more precise and delineated reconstruction of the original point cloud geometry. The fourth transpose convolution layer is a special case of sparse transpose convolution where the convolution generates new coordinates before aggregating features [11]. The new coordinates are generated on the voxels the kernel covers during convolution around the input coordinates. In PU-Dense this layer is followed by standard FE Unit and subsequent convolution-FE Unit layers since the main goal of the system is to upsample a point cloud. We instead want to reconstruct the point cloud. This is why we employ a single Inception module to reduce the feature space dimension to 1. A pruning layer reduces the number of points by selecting the top- k points in the cloud (we empirically tuned this parameter to $k = 10^6$). The FE Unit processes point cloud and then is summed up with the first layer processed voxelized point cloud, namely E_1 in Figure 2. To finally reconstruct the point cloud, a first sparse convolution layer with stride=1 is applied. Then, we repeatedly apply the pruning strategy described before. In this

Fig. 3. Our continual learning framework. During test time, we dynamically adapt the learned model with few learning epochs. Initially, the model undergoes training with a few learning epochs to reconstruct the online-accumulated point clouds, using the most recent point cloud as a query. This phase fine-tunes the model’s understanding of geometry. Then, the segmentation head is kept up-to-date by training the model to reconstruct and label point clouds from the original training set where point clouds possess ground truth labels. The \downarrow denotes that the point cloud PC is downsampled.

the learning rate using an Exponential Scheduling Rate. Each epoch is divided in three phases: (i) online point cloud reconstruction, (ii) training set point cloud reconstruction and semantic segmentation, (iii) gradient update. Fig. 3 visually describes the three phases. The first phase randomly samples a point cloud from the n just collected clouds and apply the same training reconstruction pipeline described in Section III-D, i.e. accumulate point clouds based on ego-motion odometry, downsample both clouds, let the model reconstruct the accumulated cloud just by prompting it with the latest cloud. The BCE reconstruction loss is computed and stored. The goal of this phase is to let the system adapt to the different distribution in the geometry of the point cloud. The training set often is not big enough to perfectly represent the whole world geometry situation, thus this fine-tuning is expected to bring relevant information to the following segmentation task. The second phase randomly samples a point cloud from the training set point clouds and apply a single training epoch, i.e. reconstruction and semantic segmentation (ground truth for this point cloud is available). The goal of this phase is to let the model not to forget what it learnt and not to mainly focus on reconstruction only. Both reconstruction and segmentation losses are computed and stored. The third is the gradient update step. The losses computed in the previous two steps are summed up and the computed gradients are back-propagated to update the model weights.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this short paper, we have presented our new approach to address the task of semantic segmentation in 3D point clouds, particularly in the context of autonomous driving. Our work is most focused on developing a model that is able to dynamically adapt during test time to the new environment in which it is operating in order to bridge the gap between training and test data distribution. Our method leverages 3D sparse convolutions and introduces an online learning framework, allowing for on-the-fly adaptation by exploiting the geometry

information. Preliminary qualitative experiments on publicly available datasets are supporting our intuitions.

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